

Kinetics of Ce(IV) Oxidation of Diethyl Ketone in Sulphuric Acid Solutions

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The kinetic data on Ce(IV) oxidation of diethyl ketone in sulphuric acid solutions at four temperatures show first order dependence of the reaction on both Ce(IV) and diethyl ketone. The reaction rate decreases on increasing the ionic strength of the medium while it increases on increasing the concentration of hydrogen ions. The reaction rate is unaffected by the change in concentration of both sulphate and bisulphate ions.

FEW ketones have already been subjected to kinetic studies with interest because of their various possible species involved in reactions. Earlier workers¹⁻⁶ have reported kinetic data on oxidation of ketones by different oxidants including Ce(IV) in various media. Shorter⁶ has made comparative survey of the reactivities and stoichiometry for acetaldehyde and a series of ketones including diethyl ketone at 70°, but he has not made detailed study of kinetics and mechanism of Ce(IV) oxidation of diethyl ketone. In the present communication an attempt has been made to obtain the kinetic data for the reaction between Ce(IV) and diethyl ketone in the temperature range 35°-50°.

Experimental

Materials and Method: Diethyl ketone (Fluka) grade and ceric sulphate (E. Merck) G.R. quality were used as such without further purification. Other chemicals e.g. ferrous ammonium sulphate, sulphuric acid and potassium sulphate were of A. R. (B. D. H.) grade and samples of sodium hydrogen sulphate and ferrouin were of (Sarabhai, M) and (E. Merck) respectively but samples of perchloric acid and sodium perchlorate were of (Riedel) grade.

A stock solution of ceric sulphate was prepared by direct weighing in 5N H₂SO₄ and was standardised against ferrous ammonium sulphate using ferrouin as redox indicator.

The reaction was initiated by adding a temperature equilibrated solution of diethyl ketone to a reaction vessel (maintained at desired temperature) containing the required amounts of sulphuric acid, ceric sulphate solution and water. The kinetics were followed by removing 5 ml aliquots after different intervals of time and quenching the reaction by known excess of ferrous ammonium sulphate solution. The excess of ferrous ammonium sulphate was estimated by standard ceric sulphate solution using ferrouin as redox indicator.

Results and Discussion

Stoichiometry: The equivalents of Ce(IV) used per mole of ketone was found to be 14 at 40° in 2N sulphuric acid and reaction products identified by TLC are propionic and acetic acids. These results suggest that before triketone is formed as assumed by shorter⁶, diketone probably undergoes fission and thus other methylene group escapes the attack.

Dependence of Reaction on Reactants: About sixfold variation in Ce(IV) concentration (Table 1) showed that order in Ce(IV) is one. Straight lines were obtained by plotting log [Ce(IV)]_t versus time and the pseudo-first order constants were calculated from the slopes of these lines (Fig 1).

TABLE-1						
Temperature 40° ;	[Diethyl ketone] = 4.00 × 10 ⁻² M [H ₂ SO ₄] = 2.00N					
[Ceric sulphate] × 10 ³ N—	5.00	4.00	2.50	2.00	1.66	1.34
k ₁ × 10 ³ min ⁻¹	—12.08	12.06	13.24	12.28	12.67	12.15
Average value of k ₁ = 12.41 × 10 ⁻³ min ⁻¹						

About sixfold variation in diethyl ketone concentration (Table 2) showed that pseudo-first order rate constants in Ce(IV) were directly proportional to diethyl ketone concentrations. The constancy of k₂ values (second order rate constants) shown in last column of Table 2 clearly indicates that reaction follows first order kinetics in diethyl ketone also.

TABLE-2						
Temperature 40° ;	[Ceric sulphate] = 2.00 × 10 ⁻³ N ; [H ₂ SO ₄] = 2.00N					
[Diethyl ketone] × 10 ² M—	10.00	6.66	5.00	4.00	2.50	1.66
k ₁ × 10 ³ min ⁻¹	—32.49	20.70	15.11	12.37	7.95	5.08
k ₂ × 10 ¹ l. mole ⁻¹ min ⁻¹	—3.25	3.11	3.02	3.09	3.18	3.05
Average value of k ₂ = 3.10 ± 10 ⁻¹ l. mole ⁻¹ min ⁻¹						

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Fig. 1.

Temperature 40°
 [Diethyl ketone] = $4.00 \times 10^{-3} M$
 [Sulphuric Acid] = $2.00 N$

[Ceric sulphate] $10^{-3} N$

A = 5.00
 B = 4.00
 C = 2.50
 D = 2.00
 E = 1.66
 F = 1.33

Plot	$10^3 \times K_1 \text{ min}^{-1}$ (from the slope)
A	12.09
B	12.06
C	13.24
D	12.28
E	12.67
F	12.15

Effect of Ionic Strength, Sulphate, Bisulphate and Hydrogen Ions

The reaction velocity decreased to the extent of 25% on increasing the ionic strength of the medium by six times. This substantial change in rate could not be explained specially when ionic strength variation falls beyond Debye-Hückel limiting law. About tenfold variation in the concentrations of both sulphate and bisulphate ions did not produce

any perceptible change in rate (Table 3), which is different from usual observations made by earlier workers⁷⁻¹³. The reaction velocity increased more than two times on increasing the concentration of sulphuric acid from 1.5 to 6.0 N. This increase is definitely due to hydrogen ions as sulphate and bisulphate ions do not affect the rate. This observation was, further, confirmed by variation of perchloric acid¹⁹⁻²⁰ at fixed concentration of sulphuric acid and constant ionic strength. A ten-

fold variation in perchloric acid concentration enhanced the velocity by about twofold. A graph between Δk_1 (difference between rate constants of the reaction with perchloric acid and without perchloric acid) and $\Delta[H^+]$ (difference of hydrogen ions in presence of perchloric acid and in absence of perchloric acid) was plotted. A straight line passing through origin clearly indicates the positive effect of hydrogen ions.

Fig. 2

Temperature 40°
 [Diethyl Ketone] = $4.00 \times 10^{-2} M$
 [Ceric sulphate] = $2.00 \times 10^{-2} N$
 [Sulphuric acid] = 2.00 N
 $\mu = 3.024 M$

Kinetic data on temperature effect were given in Table 3. The values of energy of activation (ΔE), entropy of activation (ΔS^\ddagger), free energy (ΔF^\ddagger) and frequency factor (A) are 18.5 K. cal/mole, -1.2 E.U., 22.3 K. cal/mole and $33.1 \times 10^9 \text{ l. mole}^{-1} \text{ sec}^{-1}$ respectively.

Ketones provide three possible real sites of attack viz. either negative, neutral or positive forms. The positive form is ruled out on the basis of transfer of electrons from ketone to ceric species in ceric sulphate oxidation of ketones. Our kinetic results do not allow us to assume the negative ion to be active form of ketone (the condition for which is that hydrogen ion concentration⁴ should lower the rate). Therefore, enol (neutral) form of ketone is only obvious choice for the real site of attack. Earlier workers^{4,21,22} also support this postulate.

Cerium(IV) has been reported to exist in many species by earlier workers^{23,24}. $[Ce(SO_4)]^{2+}$, $Ce(SO_4)_2$ and $[Ce(SO_4)_3]^{2-}$ species of Ce(IV) have been shown in equilibria by Hardwick and Robertson¹⁹ in sulphuric acid solution. Hargreaves and Sutcliffe²⁵ have also suggested some equilibria involving $[HCe(SO_4)_4]^{2-}$, $[H_2Ce(SO_4)_4]^{2-}$, $[H_3Ce(SO_4)_4]^-$ and $H_4Ce(SO_4)_4$ ions to explain mechanism of certain reactions. Our observations lead us to assume that $[HCe(SO_4)_3]^-$ is the reactive species. Absorption spectra studies of Bugaenko and Hwang Kuan-Lin (*Russ. J. Inorg. Chem.* (1963) 8, 1299) also support this. The proposed reactive species (1) i.e. $[HCe(SO_4)_3]^-$ is supposed to be in equilibrium with another species (2) as given below.

TABLE-3
 [Ceric sulphate] = $2.00 \times 10^{-2} N$; [Diethyl ketone] = $4.00 \times 10^{-2} M$; $\mu = 3.024 M$

Temp. in °C	[H ₂ SO ₄] N	[HClO ₄] N	[K ₂ SO ₄] N ^a	[NaHSO ₄] N	k ₁ × 10 ³ min ⁻¹
40	1.5	—	—	—	4.97
"	2.0	—	—	—	4.97
"	3.0	—	—	—	6.13
"	4.0	—	—	—	7.42
"	5.0	—	—	—	8.58
"	6.0	—	—	—	10.99
40	2.0	0.20	—	—	5.35
"	"	0.40	—	—	5.60
"	"	0.60	—	—	6.79
"	"	0.80	—	—	7.78
"	"	1.00	—	—	8.51
"	"	1.50	—	—	9.69
"	"	2.00	—	—	11.49
40	2.0	—	0.01	—	10.76
"	"	—	0.02	—	11.05
"	"	—	0.04	—	10.84
"	"	—	0.08	—	10.12
"	"	—	0.10	—	10.20
40	2.0	—	—	0.2	4.86
"	"	—	—	0.4	4.72
"	"	—	—	0.8	4.84
"	"	—	—	1.2	4.85
"	"	—	—	1.6	4.83
"	"	—	—	2.0	4.97
35 b	2.0	—	—	—	6.25
45 b	"	—	—	—	15.09
50 b	"	—	—	—	25.10

a → $\mu = 1.774 M$; b → $\mu = 1.024 M$

species (2) forms a complex with the enol form of ketone. Finally the complex undergoes redox reaction.

The complete mechanism for Ce(IV) oxidation of diethyl ketone in sulphuric acid solutions may, thus, be proposed as noted below

Now by applying stationary state treatment to the concentration of complex, the above scheme leads to the following rate expression

$$\frac{-d[Ce(IV)]}{dt} = \frac{K_1 K_2 k'_2 k_3}{k_{-3}} [Ceric] [diethyl ketone] [H^+] \dots\dots(v)$$

or rate = $k_4 [Ce(IV)] [diethyl ketone] [H^+]$ (vi)
 where $k_4 = \frac{K_1 K_2 k'_2 k_3}{k_{-3}}$

Thus the rate expression (vi) fully explains our kinetic data which are not explained by any other reaction path.

When the reaction is studied at fixed concentration of hydrogen ions, the equation (vi) becomes

$$\frac{-d[Ce(IV)]}{dt} = k_2 [diethyl ketone] [Ce(IV)] \dots\dots(vii)$$

and when $[diethyl ketone] \gg [Ce(IV)]$, we have

$$\frac{-d[Ce(IV)]}{dt} = k_1 [Ce(IV)] \dots\dots(viii)$$

Equation (viii) shows that the reaction follows first order kinetics in Ce(IV) which shows the validity of our proposed mechanism.

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